

My Opinion on Addressing the Pesticide Overuse Crisis and A Call for Sustainable Agriculture

Van Schepler-Luu, International Rice Research Institute

Pesticide overuse in agriculture is a growing crisis in many developing countries, including Vietnam, the Philippines, Laos, Bangladesh, and India. This problem, driven by the pressures of intensive agriculture,

has far-reaching consequences for both the environment and human health.

“Having witnessed the effects firsthand in my father’s fields, I can attest to the severity of the issue. Where there was once a vibrant ecosystem teeming with aquatic life, now only golden snails persist. As a child, I used to collect empty pesticide bottles for pocket money, and it is a stark reminder that many from my father’s generation, including him, have developed cancer. While I lack concrete scientific evidence, I strongly believe that pesticide use plays a significant role in these health issues” (Van Schepler-Luu, International Rice Research Institute)

To address this crisis, it is imperative to reduce pesticide overuse in rice farming, a staple crop in many of these countries. One of the most effective ways to achieve this is through improved pest and disease monitoring in order to have an accurate early warning system, similar to the early warning system developed for wheat rust in Ethiopia (1). These systems can help farmers make informed decisions about when and how much pesticide to use, rather than relying on routine applications regardless of actual need. Currently, many farmers apply pesticides without accurate information on the pest threat level, often mixing multiple types and adhering to fixed schedules that do not account for the specific conditions of their fields. This indiscriminate and preventative overuse not only wastes resources but also

exacerbates the problem of pesticide resistance, water and soil pollution.

Implementing proper land use systems and seasonal breaks can also play a crucial role in reducing pest and disease pressure. Continuous cropping and uncoordinated planting times create an environment that is conducive to the proliferation of pests and diseases. By incorporating fallow periods and synchronizing planting schedules, we can disrupt the life cycles of these harmful organisms and reduce the need for chemical interventions. This approach has been applied successfully to stop the brown plant hopper, Rice grassy stunt virus, and Rice ragged stunt virus epidemic in Vietnam in the 2010s (2).

Moreover, the adoption of disease and pest-resistant crop varieties is a sustainable and effective strategy for controlling these issues. However, it is essential to use these resistant varieties strategically to ensure their long-term effectiveness and prevent the emergence of new, resistant strains of pests and diseases.

Strategies around stacking multiple disease resistance genes with different modes of action have been successfully implemented in Punjab, India, to control bacterial blight for the past 20 years (Jagjeet Lore, Punjab Agricultural University).

Another model is the use of multiline varieties or mixed varietal planting as practiced in Japan to control rice blast for extended periods

(3). By planting a multiline variety consisting of several isogenic lines (ILs) or varietal mixtures with different major genes, Japanese farmers increased host genetic diversity to avoid easy breakdown of resistance. This approach enhances biodiversity, which in turn also helps to maintain ecological balance and reduce reliance on chemical pesticides.

Using biopesticides that rely on nurturing and using natural enemies of insect pests or disease pathogens is another sustainable strategy to reduce the use of chemical pesticides. Enabling plants to associate with their rich phytobiome, which includes a vast number of beneficial microbes, would help to improve plant immunity and their resistance to pests and diseases.

The interconnectedness of environmental sustainability and food safety cannot be overstated. In the Philippines, for instance, concerns over pesticide residues on vegetables have led many people to consume more meat, which is perceived as safer. This shift not only affects public health but also has broader environmental implications, given the higher resource demands of meat production compared to plant-based foods.

Addressing the pesticide overuse crisis requires a concerted effort from all stakeholders, including governments, agricultural experts, and farmers. Governments must implement and enforce regulations that promote sustainable farming practices and provide support for

research and development of alternative pest control methods. Agricultural experts need to work closely with farmers to educate them on integrated pest management techniques and the benefits of adopting resistant crop varieties. Farmers, on their part, must be willing to embrace these new methods and move away from the heavy reliance on chemical pesticides.

In conclusion, tackling the pesticide overuse crisis is not only vital for ensuring food safety and environmental health but also for protecting the well-being of farming communities. Through collective action and a commitment to sustainable practices, we can create a future where agriculture is both productive and ecologically responsible.

Acknowledgements

The post was inspired by a recent article published by Rynan Agriculture (4). I'm grateful to Kazuki Saito for the inspiring discussion that motivated me to make this post. I am also thankful for Sophien Kamoun's guidance and support. The article was written with assistance from ChatGPT.

References

1. Early warning system for wheat rust in Ethiopia, IOP Science, <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1748-9326/ab4034>.

2. Stopping the brown plant hopper, Rice grassy stunt virus, and Rice ragged stunt virus epidemic in Vietnam, Thư Viện Pháp Luật, <https://thuvienphapluat.vn/van-ban/Tai-chinh-nha-nuoc/Quyet-dinh-846-QD-UBND-2010-ho-tro-phong-vang-lun-lun-xoan-la-lun-soc-den-Dien-Bien-203524.aspx>.
3. Multiline varieties to control rice blast in Japan, JIRCAS, https://www.jircas.go.jp/en/publication/research_results/2011_10.
4. “Vietnam’s Pesticide Crisis.” Rynan Agriculture, <https://rynanagriculture.com/news-blogs/vietnams-pesticide-crisis>.

This article is available on a CC-BY license via Zenodo.